

AN EXPERIMENT FOR DEVELOPING CO-ORDINATION ABILITY SCHOOL BOYS THROUGH ASANAS

Prof. Jaysing M. Hotkar

BPCA's College of Physical Education, Wadala Mumbai-31.

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INTRODUCTION

In India very much priority and importance are given to academic development of the children. Parents want see their child at the top of the list of in various academic areas, for the purpose, parents pressurizes their children. High expectations from parents, teachers and society can lead to excessive stress and pressure to perform well in exams. This pressure is kept students away from games and sports. It may a cause for decrease physical fitness in children. Developing coordination early in life provides numerous benefits, including, Fine and gross motor skills, cognitive development, psychomotor development. This is important to the physical educator to find various remedy to maintain and development of physical fitness in children, by considering the problem, the present research study was planned. Number of research studies was reviewed before the present experiment especially for the development of co-ordination ability of the children. During the review of the related literature, it was realized that asanas are perfect practical method for improving not only the health and fitness but also the quality of life. Because to perform asana no more place is required. During the review of related literature, it was also found that very few research studies were conducted for the development of co-ordination ability of the children through asanas. Hence, the present experiment was conducted by assuming that the Asanas may improve the coordination ability of the male students.

METHOD

Forty-six male students (n=46) from Chembur Naka Municipal School, Chembur, Mumbai, were selected randomly for the present study. The subject's age group was ranging

from 11 to 14 years. The age was determined from the record of date of birth available in the school record. Pretest Post test Control Group Design was used for the experiment; accordingly, the selected forty-six male students were randomly assigned into two equal groups viz., one experimental group (n1= 23) and one control group (n2 = 23). Group A was received specific 'Asana' training while Group B was treated as control. All the subjects of experimental and control groups were exposed to eye hand co-ordination tests i.e. ball transfer test to record the pretest data. After the completion of pre test, all the subject of experimental group were exposed to a one – and half – month (6 week) training of selected Asana practices for 45 minutes daily in the evening except Sunday and holidays. However, the subjects of the Control group were allowed to participate in recreational activities but not allowed to participate in Asana program. After the asana program of six weeks post test was conducted and data were collected.

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS

There were two groups one is control and other one was experimental group. Both groups were tested before and after the treatment. To compare the mean gain scores standard statistical technique One way ANOVA was used to test the null hypotheses.

Table No. 1: - Descriptive Statistics of Pre-Test, Post-Test of Control Group, and Experimental Group.

Tests	Groups	N	Mean	Std. Dev.
Pre Test Coordination	Control Group	22	40.3073	1.86217
	Experimental Group	22	40.6377	3.21434
Post test Coordination	Control Group	22	40.3955	1.85333
	Experimental Group	22	31.9059	9.47093

Table No.1 shows that the Mean score of pretest of Control Group is 40.307 and SD is 1.86 and the mean score of pretests of Experimental Group is 40.64 and SD is 3.21 where as in case of posttest Mean score Control Group is 40.39 and SD is 1.85 and the mean score of Experimental Group is 31.90 and SD is 9.47. The same is shown in figure No.1.

Table No. 2: - Between Group, Within Group Comparison of Control Group, and Experimental Group.

			Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Remark
Pre Test Coordination	Between Groups		1.201	1	1.201	.174	.679	$p \geq 0.05$
		Within Groups	289.793	42	6.900			
Post Test Coordination	Between Groups		792.796	1	792.796	17.025	.000	$P \leq 0.05$
		Within Groups	1955.79	42	46.567			
		Groups	8					

It can be seen in table No. 02- the value of the Sum of Squares of Pre-Test of Coordination between Groups is 1.201 with df 1, the value of Mean Square is 1.201 and the 'F' value is 0.174, which is not significant. It means the mean value of pretest of control and experimental group more or less similar to each other. In the case of Post Test Coordination between Groups, the value of the Sum of Squares is 792.796 with the 'df' '1, the value of Mean Square is 792.796 and the 'F' value is 17.025, which is significant. It indicates that the mean scores of the post-test of control and experimental groups differ significantly from each other. Thus, the stated null hypothesis i.e 'There is no significant difference in the mean scores of posttests of control and the experimental group is rejected.

Fig.1- Mean Scores of Pre Test and Post Test of Co-ordination of Control and Experimental Group.

DISCUSSION

As per the result received of pretest of co-ordination ability of the school students of control group and experimental group are nearby equal to each other but in case of post test of co-ordination ability of the school students of control group and experimental group are significantly differ with the difference of mean score of -8.50. Therefore, it can be said that the posttest co-ordination ability of experimental group is increased. It indicates that, selected Asana are helpful to improve the coordination ability of the male students of aged 11 to 14 years.

CONCLUSION

The selected Asanas are effective in improving coordination ability of the school students.

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